

SUPPLY CHAIN ANALYSIS OF BANANA IN NANDURBAR DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study was designed to measure value chain analysis of Banana in selected area of Nandurbar District, focusing on how bananas are marketed, how they are distributed among different sellers, and the prices involved. Three main marketing channels were found: Channel I (Producer – Wholesaler – Consumer in other states), Channel II (Producer – Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer), and Channel III (Producer – Exporter – Consumer in Gulf countries). The analysis shows that producers sell receive a low price of ₹11.27 per kg. In contrast, exporters get higher prices, averaging ₹26.50 per kg, indicating better profit opportunities in international markets. The price spread analysis reveals that in Channel I, producers earn 66.67% of the consumer price, while in Channel II, their share decreases to 45.85%, meaning wholesalers and retailers make more profit. In Channel III, producers receive ₹15.50 per kg, highlighting the importance of exports. Overall, the findings suggest that local producers play a vital role in the supply chain but face economic challenges and low profit margins

Keywords: Bananas, Marketing, Distribution, Marketing Channels, Producer, Wholesaler, Retailer, Exporter, Consumer, Price Analysis, Price Spread, Profit Margins, International Markets, Economic Challenges, Market Access, Infrastructure.

Introduction and Objectives:

Banana is highly consumed fruit in the world. The botanical name of banana is *Musa paradisiaca* Linn and it is highly cultivated in the Asian countries. Banana has social, economic and spiritual values. India is largest producer of banana in the world and followed by China and Indonesia. Banana holds special place in Indian agriculture sector, yield of banana gives nice income to banana farmer The cultivation of banana is done in many states of India in which Maharashtra leads in production followed by Karnataka, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh and Assam. In Maharashtra Jalgaon district produced highest banana among all the districts. The other banana growing districts are Nandurbar, Amaravati, Dhule, etc. The major contributing districts are Jalgaon, Amaravati and Nandurbar. The fruit is mostly consumed in ripen form but it has many by products such as banana powder, banana biscuits, banana chips etc., which are highly demanded in market. The leaves of banana used for serving the meal on special occasion and also used in Hindu culture for prayer.

India is leading in production of banana with production of 35.36 MMT in fiscal year 2022-23 and export around only one percent i.e. 0.36 MMT. It shows the lack of export of banana from India. The production of banana in Andhra Pradesh contributing about 67per cent in production followed by Maharashtra, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh. These are five major banana producing states of India Farmers can sell their fruit to any market in India. The fruit is sold in an unripened form. The quality of the fruit determines its selling price. Quality is assessed based on factors such as fruit size, colour, and thickness. These parameters help decide both the price and the market for the fruit. Higher quality fruit commands a higher price. The price spread of fruit is seen at each level of supply chain each step in chain added the cost of transport, storage and handling. The price of banana depends on the channel through which the banana reach to end consumer and also the demand and supply of fruit. At the local market where the cultivation of banana is practiced has short supply chain compared to other areas. The highest quality fruit is exported to Arab countries, while other fruits are sold in states like Rajasthan, Gujarat, Delhi, etc. Fruit is sold by farmers to wholesalers, retailers, and exporters according to its grade. Wholesalers generally distribute the fruit to other states. The ratoon crop produces fruit of lower quality, which is typically sold in the local Indian market at lower prices. Bananas are ripened locally in banana ripening chambers. Ripened bananas are then sold to retailers. The shelf life of unripe bananas can last up to 20 days if stored at a low temperature of around 13.5°C, in an unvented polybag with 90-95per cent relative humidity. This storage method helps in exporting bananas to other states and countries The specific objectives of the study are:

To identify the marketing of Banana.

To work out the price spread of Banana.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in Nandurbar District for the financial year 2023-24. The research involved both primary and secondary data. For study 30 farmers, 5 wholesalers, 5 retailers, and exporters were selected randomly. Primary data were gathered from farmers, wholesalers, retailers and exporters using pre-tested questioner.

Analytical Tool

Simple tabular analysis were carried out for the present study.

Results and Discussion

This study examines Supply chain analysis of Banana in Nandurbar District.

The marketing of Banana:

The three marketing channels were found during the study in Nandurbar District which are as follow:

Channel I: Producer – wholesaler – Consumer (other state)

Channel II: Producer – Wholesaler – Retailer- Consumer

Channel III: Producer – Exporter – Consumer (Gulf Countries)

Channel I: Producer – wholesaler – Consumer (other state)

This channel involved bananas being sold from the producer directly to a wholesaler, who then distributed the bananas to consumers in other states. This channel highlighted that a portion of the banana produce from Nandurbar was reaching consumers outside the state, indicating a regional market reach and potentially larger distribution networks. It also suggested that the wholesalers played a critical role in connecting the local producers with out-of-state markets.

Channel II: Producer – Wholesaler – Retailer- Consumer

In this channel, bananas moved from the producer to a wholesaler, then to a retailer, and finally to the consumer. This channel represented a more traditional supply chain structure where multiple intermediaries were involved. The presence of retailers in this channel indicated that bananas were being sold in local or regional markets through retail outlets, which could include local grocery stores, markets, or supermarkets. This channel likely facilitated direct consumer access within the local or nearby regions, contributing to broader market coverage.

Channel III: Producer – Exporter – Consumer (Gulf Countries)

This channel involved the bananas being sold from the producer to an exporter, who then exported the bananas to consumers in Gulf countries. This channel highlighted the international market reach of Nandurbar's banana production and indicated that a segment of the produce was being exported to international markets. This international channel pointed to opportunities for expanding market reach and potentially higher revenue through exports, while also suggesting that exporters played a crucial role in facilitating international trade.

The price spread of Banana

In Nandurbar district the production of Banana is higher due to the high cultivation banana. The farmers get the price of banana according to

the quality of banana. Table: Marketing Cost and Price spread of Banana in Nandurbar District.

Table: Marketing Cost and Price spread of Banana in Nandurbar District.

(Rs/Kg)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
1	Net price received by the poducer	12 (66.67)	10 (45.85)	15.50 (58.49)
2	Expenses incurred by the producer	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
3	Expenses incurred by the Wholesaler			
4	a) Harvesting	1.5 (8.33)	1.5 (6.88)	
5	b) Packing	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	
6	c) Loading	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	
7	d) Storage	0 (0.00)	0.42 (1.93)	
8	e) Transport	0.65 (3.61)	0.3 (1.38)	
9	Sub-Total	2.15 (11.94)	2.22 (10.18)	
10	Wholesalers Margin	3.85 (21.39)	2.58 (11.83)	
11	Wholesaler sale price	18	14.8 (67.86)	
12	Expenses incurred by the Retailer		0 (0.00)	
13	a) Harvesting		0 (0.00)	
14	b) Packing		0 (0.00)	
15	c) Loading		0 (0.00)	
16	d) Storage		0 (0.00)	
17	e) Transport		0 (0.00)	
18	Sub-Total		0 (0.00)	
19	Retailer Margin		7.01 (32.14)	
20	Retailer Sales price/ Consumer puurchase price		21.81	
21	Expenses incurred by the Exporter			
22	a) Harvesting			1.22 (4.60)
23	b) Packing			0 (0.00)
24	c) Loading			0.62 (2.34)
25	d) Storage			2.62 (9.89)
26	e) Transport			0.31 (1.17)
27	f) miscellaneous			1.25 (4.72)
28	Sub-Total			6.02 (22.72)
29	Exporter Margin			4.98 (18.79)
30	Exporter Selling Price			26.5
31	Price Spread	6	11.81	11

(figures in parenthesis are indicates the percentage to total)

Channel I:

The producer received ₹12 per kg, accounting for 66.67per cent of the final consumer price. The producer had no expenses. The wholesaler others. The price spread is seen in the channel I is ₹ 6.

Channel II:

In this channel, the producer received ₹10 per kg, which was 45.85per cent of the final price. The producer had no direct expenses. The wholesaler's marketing costs totaled ₹2.22 per kg, with costs for

incurred a total marketing cost of ₹2.15 per kg, covering harvesting and transport costs. The wholesaler's margin was ₹3.85, leading to a final selling price of ₹18. This channel demonstrated a relatively highmargin for the wholesaler and lower marketing costs compared to

storage and transport included. The wholesaler's margin was ₹2.58. The retailer added a significant margin of ₹7.01, resulting in a consumer purchase price of ₹21.81. This channel had higher costs and

margins, particularly at the retail stage. The price spread is seen in the channel I is ₹ 11.81

Channel III:

For Channel III, the producer received ₹15.5 per kg, which was 58.49per cent of the final price. The producer incurred no expenses. The exporter's total marketing costs amounted to ₹6.02 per kg, including significant costs for storage, transport, and miscellaneous expenses. The exporter's margin was ₹4.98, with a final selling price of ₹26.5. The marketing efficiency was 0.84, indicating lower efficiency compared to Channel II. The price spread is seen in the channel I is ₹ 11

Conclusion

The marketing of banana was found the three main channel in the research which are as follow:

Channel I: Producer – wholesaler – Consumer (other state)

Channel II: Producer – Wholesaler – Retailer- Consumer

Channel III: Producer – Exporter – Consumer (Gulf Countries)

In the channel I the producer received ₹10 per kg, which was 45.85per cent of the final price This channel demonstrated a relatively high margin for the wholesaler and lower marketing costs compared to others. In the channel II producer received the ₹15.5 per kg, which was 58.49per cent of the final price. The producer incurred no expenses This channel had higher costs and margins, particularly at the retail stage. In the channel III the producer received ₹15.5 per kg, which was 58.49per cent of the final price. The exporter's margin was ₹4.98, with a final selling price of ₹26.5. The marketing efficiency was 0.84, indicating lower efficiency compared to Channel II.

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